

Appendix C

AI-Driven Multi-Modal Graphs for Targeted Metabolite Discovery

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Supplementary Fig. 1. Charge migration reactions considered in MAPLE *in silico* fragmentation prediction. These reactions involve relocation of the charged site, leading to bond cleavage during MS/MS fragmentation. Each reaction is encoded using SMARTS notation, with R-groups representing variable atoms. See accompanying code for implementation details.

Remote Hydrogen Rearrangement 1

Remote Hydrogen Rearrangement 2

Retro-Dies-Alder

Retro-ene (includes Mclafferty Rearrangement)

Carbon Monoxide Elimination

Pericyclic Process

Charge Remote Fragmentation

Aromatic Elimination

Supplementary Fig. 2. Charge retention reactions considered in MAPLE *in silico* fragmentation prediction. These reactions do not involve the charged site but still result in the loss of a molecular fragment. Each reaction is encoded using SMARTS notation, with R-groups representing variable atoms. See accompanying code for implementation details.

Supplementary Fig. 3. Rearrangement reactions considered in MAPLE *in silico* fragmentation prediction. These reactions do not result in the loss of a molecular fragment but may enable subsequent charge migration or retention reactions. Each reaction is encoded using SMARTS notation, with R-groups representing variable atoms. See accompanying code for implementation details.

Supplementary Fig. 4. Distribution of media components, primary metabolites, and specialized metabolites based on genus consistency scores. This score measures how frequently a given genus appears among the producers of related metabolites retrieved using MS1Former embeddings. Examples of known specialized metabolites with strong genus-specific associations are presented. Additional examples are listed in Supplementary Table 5.

Supplementary Fig. 5. The structure of streptosiderin and the selected COSY and HMBC correlations.

Supplementary Fig. 6. ^1H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ of streptosiderin

Supplementary Fig. 7. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ of streptosiderin

Supplementary Fig. 8. ¹H-¹H COSY spectrum in DMSO- d₆ of streptosiderin

Supplementary Fig. 9. HSQC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d₆ of streptosiderin

Supplementary Fig. 10. HMBC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d₆ of streptosiderin

Supplementary Fig. 11. MS/MS spectrum of streptosiderin

Supplementary Fig. 12. The structure of pectobactin and the selected COSY and HMBC correlations.

Supplementary Fig. 13. Substructures of pectobactin based on its MS/MS spectrum.

Supplementary Fig. 14. ¹H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in DMSO- d₆ of pectobactin

Supplementary Fig. 15. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of pectobactin

Supplementary Fig. 16. $^1\text{H-}^1\text{H}$ COSY spectrum in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of pectobactin

Supplementary Fig. 17. HSQC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of pectobactin

Supplementary Fig. 18. HMBC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of pectobactin

Supplementary Fig. 19. NOESY NMR spectrum in DMSO- d₆ of pectobactin

Supplementary Fig. 20. NOESY NMR spectrum in DMSO- d₆ of pectobactin

Supplementary Fig. 21. The structure of szentamide B and the selected COSY and HMBC correlations.

Supplementary Fig. 22. ^1H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of szentamide B

Supplementary Fig. 23. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of szentamide B

Supplementary Fig. 24. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of szentamide B

Supplementary Fig. 24. HSQC NMR spectrum in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of szentamide B

Supplementary Fig. 25. HMBC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of szentamide B

Supplementary Fig. 26. HRESIMS spectrum of szentamide B

Supplementary Fig. 29. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of piericidin S

Supplementary Fig. 30. $^1\text{H-}^1\text{H}$ COSY spectrum in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of piericidin S

Supplementary Fig. 31. HSQC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of piericidin S

Supplementary Fig. 32. HMBC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of piericidin S

Supplementary Fig. 33. NOESY NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of piericidin S

Supplementary Fig. 34. HRESIMS spectrum of piericidin S

Supplementary Fig. 35. Novel NRPS BGC identified exclusively in the Morganeliaceae family. The BGC encodes a quintipeptide composed of valine and leucine. This scaffold is conserved across five *Xenorhabdus* and seven *Photorhabdus* genomes, with corresponding BGCs shown. IBIS is used for BGC detection and annotation. The BGC outlined with a dotted box is selected for targeted metabolite discovery. Abbreviations: Valine (Val), Leucine (Leu), Thiolation (T), Serine (Ser), 2-aminobutyric acid (Abu), Condensation (C), Thioesterase (TE), Nonribosomal Peptide (NRPS), Biosynthetic Gene Cluster (BGC).

Supplementary Fig. 36. Aligning MAPLE *in silico* fragmentation of predicted linear peptide from BGC with experimental MS/MS spectrum. Among the metabolites predicted as NRPS by MS2Former, this metabolite exhibited the highest number of annotated fragments (highlighted in orange) and was therefore selected for isolation. Abbreviations: Valine (Val), Leu (Leucine), Condensation (C), Thiolation (T), Thioesterase (TE), Biosynthetic Gene Cluster (BGC).

Supplementary Fig. 37. The structure of xenomibactin A and the selected COSY and HMBC correlations.

xenomibactin A		
	Calculated	Experimental
Y1	637	637.4645
Y2	538	538.3907
Y3	439	439.3231
Y4	326	326.2427
Y5	213	213.1592

The figure shows the linear structure of xenomibactin A with five substructures labeled Y1 through Y5. Vertical dashed lines separate the residues, and arrows point from the labels Y1 to Y5 to the corresponding residues in the structure. The Y5 residue is shown as a protonated imino group (C=NH⁺).

Supplementary Fig. 38. Substructures of xenomibactin A based on their MS/MS spectrum.

Supplementary Fig. 39. ^1H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of xenomibactin A

Supplementary Fig. 40. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of xenomibactin A

Supplementary Fig. 41. ¹H-¹H COSY spectrum in DMSO- d₆ of xenomibactin A

Supplementary Fig. 42. HSQC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d₆ of xenomibactin A

Supplementary Fig. 43. HMBC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of xenomibactin A

Supplementary Fig. 44. NOESY NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of xenomibactin A

Observed Biosynthetic Gene Cluster

Biosynthetic Breakdown of Molecule

Supplementary Fig. 45. Biosynthetic breakdown of xenomibactin with alignment to adenylation domains identified in the corresponding BGC. Four of the five amino acids are correctly predicted in order, with one misclassification. Abbreviations: Valine (Val), Leu (Leucine), Condensation (C), Thiolation (T), Thioesterase (TE), Biosynthetic Gene Cluster (BGC).

xenomibactin B

xenomibactin C

Supplementary Fig. 46. The structure of xenomibactin B-C, and the selected COSY and HMBC correlations.

	xenomibactin B		xenomibactin C	
	Calculated	Experimental	Calculated	Experimental
Y1	705	705.4335	739	739.4200
Y2	606	606.3651	641	641.3851
Y3	507	507.2984	541	541.2775
Y4	394	394.2137	394	394.2140
Y5	247	247.1450	247	247.1431

Supplementary Fig. 47. Substructures of xenomibactin B-C based on their MS/MS spectrum.

Supplementary Fig. 48. ¹H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in DMSO-d₆ of xenomibactin B.

Supplementary Fig. 49. ¹³C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in DMSO-d₆ of xenomibactin B

Supplementary Fig. 50. ¹H-¹H COSY spectrum in DMSO-d₆ of xenomibactin B

Supplementary Fig. 51. HSQC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of xenomibactin B

Supplementary Fig. 52. HMBC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of xenomibactin B

Supplementary Fig. 53. NOESY NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of xenomibactin B

Supplementary Fig. 54. ^1H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in DMSO- d_6 of xenomibactin C

Supplementary Fig. 55. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in DMSO- d_6 of xenomibactin C

Supplementary Fig. 56. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of xenomibactin C

Supplementary Fig. 57. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in DMSO-d_6 of xenomibactin C

Supplementary Fig. 58. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in DMSO-d_6 of xenomibactin C

Supplementary Fig. 59. NOESY NMR spectrum in DMSO- d6 of xenomibactin C

Supplementary Fig. 60. Biosynthetic mapping of the T1PKS macrolide deoxyerythromycin C using BLOOM. This example illustrates the precise mapping of small carbon precursor units in T1PKS biosynthesis, identifying the directionality relative to ester bonds. BLOOM incorporates flexible substructure motifs (denoted with R groups) to account for post-assembly tailoring modifications, such as hydroxylation. The molecular regions are enumerated and color-coded according to the provided legend. Abbreviations: Methyl-Malonyl-CoA (MeMal), Ketoreductase (KR), Enoylreductase (ER), Thioesterase (TE), Type 1 Polyketide (T1PKS).

Supplementary Fig. 61. Biosynthetic mapping of the T1PKS linear ganefromycin using BLOOM. BLOOM leverages the biosynthetic context of neighboring functional units to improve the accuracy of substructure mapping. This approach is particularly effective for modeling nucleophilic epoxide ring-opening reactions initiated by the hydroxyl group of Mal-KR. Furthermore, context-based mapping enables the identification of intramolecular aldol-type cyclizations between isoBut-KR and MeMal-KS, wherein a hydroxyl nucleophile attacks a ketone electrophile. Abbreviations: Malonyl-CoA (Mal), Methyl-Malonyl-CoA (MeMal), iso-Butyryl-CoA (isoBut), Ketosynthase (KS), Ketoreductase (KR), Dehydratase (DH), Thioesterase (TE), Glycine (Gly), Polyether (PE), Type 1 Polyketide (T1PKS).

Supplementary Fig. 62. Biosynthetic mapping of the T1PKS linear kalimantacin A using BLOOM. The mapping highlights key biosynthetic features, including β -branch insertion and amino acid incorporation, which contribute to increased chemical diversity. Abbreviations: Malonyl-CoA (Mal), Ketosynthase (KS), Ketoreductase (KR), Dehydratase (DH), Enoylreductase (ER), β -branch (B), Glycine (Gly), Type 1 Polyketide (T1PKS).

Supplementary Fig. 63. Biosynthetic mapping of the T1PKS leptolyngbyalide B using BLOOM. The mapping highlights key biosynthetic features, including β -branch insertion, epoxide ring opening leading to intramolecular cyclization, and fatty acid tailoring modifications. Abbreviations: Malonyl-CoA (Mal), Methyl-Malonyl-CoA (MeMal), Ketoreductase (KR), β -branch (B), Thioesterase (TE), Type 1 Polyketide (T1PKS).

Supplementary Fig. 64. Biosynthetic mapping of the T1PKS polyether monensin A using BLOOM. Context-based substructure mapping enables the identification of consecutive epoxide ring-opening events, a characteristic feature of polyether biosynthesis. BLOOM reconstructs the original biosynthetic chain from modular assembly-line enzymes, resolving complexity introduced by downstream tailoring reactions and cyclization patterns. This capability allows for the grouping of biosynthetically related scaffolds. Abbreviations: Malonyl-CoA (Mal), Methyl-Malonyl-CoA (MeMal), Ethyl-Malonyl-CoA (EtMal), Ketosynthase (KS), Ketoreductase (KR), Enoylreductase (ER), Thioesterase (TE), Type 1 Polyketide (T1PKS).

Supplementary Fig. 65. Biosynthetic mapping of the T1PKS polyether moyukamycin using BLOOM. The mapping reveals key biosynthetic features, including intramolecular aldol-type cyclizations between MeMal-KR and Mal-KR, which trigger a cascade of downstream epoxide ring-opening events and culminate in an additional aldol-type cyclization. Such transformations highlight the propensity of ketoreduced units within polyketide scaffolds to participate in cyclization reactions. Additionally, post-tailoring enzymatic modifications can induce shifts in double bond positions, as seen with MeMal-DH-TE. BLOOM accounts for these alterations by mapping dimeric substructures that reflect the modified unsaturation pattern. Abbreviations: Malonyl-CoA (Mal), Methyl-Malonyl-CoA (MeMal), Hydroxy-Methyl-Malonyl-CoA (OHMeMal), Ketosynthase (KS), Ketoreductase (KR), Enoylreductase (ER), Dehydratase (DH), Double Bond Shift (DS), Type 1 Polyketide (T1PKS).

Supplementary Fig. 66. Biosynthetic mapping of the T1PKS macrolide niphithricin A using BLOOM. The mapping reveals key biosynthetic features, including aldol-type intramolecular cyclizations and the incorporation of unconventional starter units (e.g., guanidinobutyrate). Abbreviations: Hydroxy-Malonyl-CoA (OHMal), Methyl-Malonyl-CoA (MeMal), Malonyl-CoA (Mal), Ketosynthase (KS), Ketoreductase (KR), Dehydratase (DH), Enoylreductase (ER), Thioesterase (TE), Type 1 Polyketide (T1PKS).

Supplementary Fig. 67. Biosynthetic mapping of the T1PKS polyene nystatin using BLOOM. The mapping reveals conjugated double bonds generated through successive dehydration reactions during polyketide assembly. Abbreviations: Malonyl-CoA (Mal), Methyl-Malonyl-CoA (MeMal), Ketosynthase (KS), Ketoreductase (KR), Dehydratase (DH), Enoylreductase (ER), Thioesterase (TE), Type 1 Polyketide (T1PKS).

Supplementary Fig. 68. Biosynthetic mapping of the spiral T1PKS oligomycin A using BLOOM. The mapping reveals the characteristic helical polycyclic structure and the corresponding biosynthetic assembly line responsible for its construction. Abbreviations: Malonyl-CoA (Mal), Methyl-Malonyl-CoA (MeMal), Ethyl-Malonyl-CoA (EtMal), Ketosynthase (KS), Ketoreductase (KR), Dehydratase (DH), Enoylreductase (ER), Thioesterase (TE), Type 1 Polyketide (T1PKS).

Supplementary Fig. 69. Biosynthetic mapping of the linear T1PKS ripostatin C using BLOOM. The mapping reveals an incomplete β -branching cascade resulting from a missing decarboxylation step. Abbreviations: Malonyl-CoA (Mal), Methyl-Malonyl-CoA (MeMal), Ketosynthase (KS), Ketoreductase (KR), Dehydratase (DH), Enoylreductase (ER), β -branch (B), Type 1 Polyketide (T1PKS).

Supplementary Fig. 70. Novel 16-membered T1PKS BGCS from *Chitinophaga* sp. C408L identified by IBIS, featuring multiple β -branching sites. Auxiliary genes encode enzymes required for β -branching (e.g., T, HCS, ECH). Several T1PKS modules contain ER domains in the absence of KR and DH domains, indicating that β -branching may occur at these sites, followed by subsequent reductions. A schematic of the β -branching mechanism is presented, illustrating each enzymatic step and the incorporation of the C-2 carbon from malonyl-CoA. T1PKS modules containing KR generate monomers with hydroxyl groups, which serve as ionization sites for MS/MS fragmentation. As such, the resulting metabolite is an ideal candidate for biosynthetic class prediction using MS2Former. Abbreviations: Hydroxymethylglutaryl-CoA synthase (HCS), Enoyl-CoA hydratase (ECH), Thiolation (T), Thioesterase (TE), EC 4.1.1.87 decarboxylase (4.1) Ketosynthase (KS), Ketoreductase (KR), Dehydratase (DH), Enoylreductase (ER), Acyl hydrolase (AH), Malonyl-CoA (Mal), Type 1 Polyketide (T1PKS), Biosynthetic Gene Cluster (BGC).

Supplementary Fig. 71. The structure of chitinolide, and the selected COSY and HMBC correlations.

Supplementary Fig. 72. ^1H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of chitinolide

Supplementary Fig. 73. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of chitinolide

Supplementary Fig. 74. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of chitinolide

Supplementary Fig. 75. HSQC NMR spectrum in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of chitinolide

Supplementary Fig. 76. HMBC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of chitinolide

Supplementary Fig. 77. TOCSY NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of chitinolide

Supplementary Fig. 78. HRESIMS spectrum of chitinolide

Observed Biosynthetic Gene Cluster

Biosynthetic Breakdown of Molecule

Supplementary Fig. 79. Biosynthetic breakdown of chitinolide with alignment to T1PKS modules identified in the corresponding BGC. The molecular backbone predominantly aligns with genomically predicted KR and β -branching modules, supporting a plausible association between the BGC and the observed metabolite. Abbreviations: Hydroxymethylglutaryl-CoA synthase (HCS), Enoyl-CoA hydratase (ECH), Thiolation (T), Thioesterase (TE), EC 4.1.1.87 decarboxylase (4.1) Ketosynthase (KS), Ketoreductase (KR), Dehydratase (DH), Enoylreductase (ER), Acyl hydrolase (AH), Malonyl-CoA (Mal), Methyl-Malonyl-CoA (MeMal), β -branch (B), Type 1 Polyketide (T1PKS), Biosynthetic Gene Cluster (BGC).